

ISic1209

Epitaph of Philisto

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

From the area of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8790

Physical Description

A rectangular sandstone cippus, slightly damaged on the lower left corner

Dimensions

Height 43.5 cm

Width 30.5 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

Single line of Greek letters across the middle of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Regular plain letters. Phi is slightly taller than the rest, but with a small circular eye; sigma has horizontal top and bottom bars, with the diagonals joined by a curve; omicron is smaller than the other letters and mid-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30-35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Φιλιστοῦς

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Philisto

Commentary

The name Φιλιστώ [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%A6%CE%B9%CE%BB%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CF%8E] is not

common; it is also attested in Sicily in the theatre seat inscriptions of ISic1262 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1262>] (Taormina). Although dated on the grounds of letter forms to the C2-1 BC by Manni Piraino, the evidence from the necropolis suggests the range C3-2 BC is more plausible.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492813

EDR 147869

EDCS 39101573

PHI 140693

PHI 175726

Bibliography

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